

**TRANSLATION-INVARIANT GROUND STATES FOR THE CHUI–WEEKS
MODEL WITH FOUR SPIN STATES ON A CAYLEY TREE OF ORDER
TWO**

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Abstract: In this work, the four-state Chui-Weeks model on the second-order Cayley tree is considered. For this model, all translation-invariant ground states are described.

Key words: Cayley tree, Chui-Weeks model, ground state, translation-invariant ground state.

In the present work, the four-state Chui-Weeks model is considered on a second-order Cayley tree for the first time and for this model, all translation-invariant ground states are described. The three-state Chui-Weeks model on Cayley trees was studied in [1-3].

The Cayley tree Γ^k (see, e.g., [4]) of order $k \geq 1$ is an infinite tree, i.e., a graph without cycles, from each vertex of which exactly $k + 1$ edges issue. Let $\Gamma^k = (V, L, i)$, where V is the set of vertices of Γ^k , L is the set of edges of Γ^k and i is the incidence function associating each edge $l \in L$ with its endpoints $x, y \in V$. If $i(l) = \{x, y\}$, then x and y are called nearest neighboring vertices, and we write $l = \langle x, y \rangle$.

We consider the model where the spin takes values in the set $\Phi = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$. For $A \subseteq V$ a spin configuration σ_A on A is defined as a function $x \in A \rightarrow \sigma_A(x) \in \Phi$; the set of all configurations coincides with $\Omega_A = \Phi^A$. Denote $\Omega = \Omega_V$ and $\sigma = \sigma_V$.

Definition 1. A configuration that is invariant with respect to all shifts is called translation-invariant.

The Chui-Weeks model (see [1]) is defined by the following Hamiltonian

$$H(\sigma) = J \sum_{\langle x,y \rangle \in L} |\sigma(x) - \sigma(y)| + \alpha \sum_{x \in V} \delta_{\sigma(x),0}, \quad (1)$$

where $J, \alpha \in \mathbb{R}$, α is an external field and $\sigma \in \Omega$.

Remark 1. Recall that model (1) coincides with the SOS model under the condition $\alpha = 0$ (see, e.g., [4]).

Let M be the set of all unit balls with vertices in V and $S_1(x)$ be the set of all nearest neighboring vertices of $x \in V$.

We call the restriction of a configuration to the ball $b \in M$ a bounded configuration σ_b . The energy of configuration σ_b on b is defined by the formula

$$U(\sigma_b) = \frac{J}{2} \sum_{x \in S_1(c_b)} |\sigma(x) - \sigma(c_b)| + \frac{\alpha}{k+2} \sum_{x \in b} \delta_{\sigma(x),0}.$$

where $J = (J, \alpha) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and c_b is the center of the unit ball b .

The Hamiltonian (1) can be written as

$$H(\sigma) = \sum_{b \in M} U(\sigma_b).$$

Now we study translation-invariant ground states for the four-state Chui-Weeks model on the Cayley tree of order two.

We have the following lemma.

Lemma 1. Let $k = 2$. Then for each configuration φ_b , we have the following

$$U(\varphi_b) \in \{U_i : i = 1, 2, \dots, 29\},$$

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where

$$U_1 = 0; U_2 = \alpha; U_3 = \frac{J}{2}; U_4 = \frac{J}{2} + \frac{\alpha}{4}; U_5 = \frac{J}{2} + \frac{3\alpha}{4}; U_6 = J; U_7 = J + \frac{\alpha}{4};$$

$$U_8 = J + \frac{\alpha}{2}; U_9 = J + \frac{3\alpha}{4}; U_{10} = \frac{3J}{2}; U_{11} = \frac{3J}{2} + \frac{\alpha}{4}; U_{12} = \frac{3J}{2} + \frac{\alpha}{2};$$

$$U_{13} = \frac{3J}{2} + \frac{3\alpha}{4}; U_{14} = 2J; U_{15} = 2J + \frac{\alpha}{4}; U_{16} = 2J + \frac{\alpha}{2}; U_{17} = \frac{5J}{2};$$

$$U_{18} = \frac{5J}{2} + \frac{\alpha}{4}; U_{19} = \frac{5J}{2} + \frac{\alpha}{2}; U_{20} = 3J; U_{21} = 3J + \frac{\alpha}{4}; U_{22} = 3J + \frac{\alpha}{2};$$

$$U_{23} = 3J + \frac{3\alpha}{4}; U_{24} = \frac{7J}{2} + \frac{\alpha}{4}; U_{25} = \frac{7J}{2} + \frac{\alpha}{2}; U_{26} = 4J + \frac{\alpha}{4}; U_{27} = 4J + \frac{\alpha}{2};$$

$$U_{28} = \frac{9J}{2} + \frac{\alpha}{4}; U_{29} = \frac{9J}{2} + \frac{3\alpha}{4}.$$

Definition 2. A configuration φ is called a ground state for the Hamiltonian (1), if

$$U(\varphi_b) = \min\{U_i; i = 1, 2, \dots, 29\}$$

for any $b \in M$.

We denote

$$A_\xi = \{(J, \alpha) \in R^2: U_\xi = \min\{U_i; i = 1, 2, \dots, 29\}\}.$$

Calculations show that:

$$A_1 = \{(J, \alpha) \in R^2: J \geq 0, \alpha \geq 0\}; A_2 = \{(J, \alpha) \in R^2: 18J \geq \alpha, \alpha \leq 0\};$$

$$A_3 = A_6 = A_{10} = A_{14} = A_{17} = \{(J, \alpha) \in R^2: J = 0, \alpha \geq 0\};$$

$$A_4 = A_5 = A_7 = A_8 = A_9 = A_{11} = A_{12} = A_{13} = A_{15} = A_{16} = A_{18} = A_{19} = A_{21} = A_{22} = \dots = A_{27} = \{(J, \alpha) \in R^2: J = 0, \alpha = 0\};$$

$$A_{20} = \{(J, \alpha) \in R^2: -\alpha \leq 6J \leq 0\}; A_{28} = \{(J, \alpha) \in R^2: 0 \leq \alpha \leq -6J\};$$

$$A_{29} = \{(J, \alpha) \in R^2: 18J \leq \alpha \leq 0\};$$

and $\bigcup_{i=1}^{29} A_i = R^2$.

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The following theorem describes all translation-invariant ground states for the four-state Chui-Weeks model on the Cayley tree of order two.

Theorem 1. Let $k = 2$. Then, for the four-state Chui-Weeks model, the following assertions hold:

(i) The configurations $\sigma(x) = i, i \in \{1,2,3\}$, for for all $x \in V$ are translation-invariant ground states iff $(J, \alpha) \in A_1$;

(ii) The configuration $\sigma(x) = 0$ for all $x \in V$ is the translation-invariant ground state iff $(J, \alpha) \in A_2$;

(iii) If $(J, \alpha) \in R^2 \setminus (A_1 \cup A_2)$, then there is no translation-invariant ground state.

Proof. Let $k = 2$.

(i) We consider the configuration $\sigma(x) = i, i \in \{1,2,3\}$, for all $x \in V$. For any $b \in M$ by Lemma we have $U(\sigma_b) = U_1 = 0$. Thus the configuration $\sigma(x) = i, i \in \{1,2,3\}$, for all $x \in V$ is ground state iff $(J, \alpha) \in A_1$;

(ii) We consider the configuration $\sigma(x) = 0$ for all $x \in V$. For any $b \in M$ by Lemma we have $U(\sigma_b) = U_2 = \alpha$. Thus the configuration $\sigma(x) = 0$ for all $x \in V$ is ground state iff $(J, \alpha) \in A_2$;

(iii) It is obvious. The theorem is proved.

LITERATURE

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